

STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING BUSINESS EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN UNIVERSITIES THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN ENUGU STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study determined Business Educators opinion on the strategies for improving Business Education programme through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested. The population of the study comprised 30 Business Educators from two government owned Universities (UNN and ESUT). The instrument was a-20 item structured questionnaire developed by the researchers entitled: Strategies for Improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire (SFIBEPITAIQ). The instrument was duly validated by three experts. The reliability was done using Cronbach Alpha which yielded coefficient of 0.69, indicating the instrument was reliable. The two research questions was answered using mean with standard deviation. While, the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test. Results of data analysis relating to the study have shown that personalized and intelligent tutoring related strategies respectively will improve Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state. The hypotheses tested, showed that there was no significant difference between the Business Educators in Federal Universities and their counterparts in State on personalized and intelligent tutoring related strategies respectively. Based on the findings, it was recommended that Business Educators should be exposed to artificial intelligence skills. Again, personalized teaching strategies should be done as a course.

KEYWORDS

Strategies, Business Education programme, Universities, Artificial Intelligence.

Introduction

The global technological innovations in the business world have brought about radical changes in the educational institutions and instructional delivery. Technology is now a new tool that sharpens the global economy and equips various courses offered in university.

A university is an institution of higher education and research that grants academic degree in various fields of study. In Enugu state, there are both Federal and State owned universities. Agbo and Ugwunwoti (2022) opined that, state Universities are owned, financed and controlled by state government and vice versa Federal Universities. According to Afolayan (2013), a university is an institution that combines teaching, research and

service to society, producing graduates equipped with skills, knowledge and value for the global market. An organized university is responsible for teaching, researching and community service. Moreover, in Universities in Nigeria, various courses are offered including Business Education.

Business Education is one of the courses offered in universities. According to the core curriculum and minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS, 2023), Business Education has options of Accounting, Marketing, Office Technology and Management (OTM) and Entrepreneurship. Business Education therefore refers to the teaching and learning of business principles, theories and practices to prepare individuals for successful careers in business, Entrepreneurship and Management.

According to Igwe (2020), Business Education is a comprehensive and integrated process of learning that enable individuals to acquire the knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary to function effectively in the Business environment. The scope of Business Education may include: Business administration, management, marketing, finance, Accounting, Entrepreneurship, Human resources, International business, E-commerce and Business ethics. Collaborating, Ugwuwoti and Aruah (2024) opined that Business Education is based on these objectives: (a) develop knowledge and skills in business management, finance, marketing and operations

(b) Foster entrepreneurship and innovation

(c) Enhance critical thinking, problem-solving and decision-making abilities

(d) Prepare students for careers in various industries and sectors. These above objectives are achievable through functional Business Education programme.

Business Education programme is a structured educational initiative that teaches students the knowledge, skills and attitudes needed to succeed in business, entrepreneurship and management, preparing them for careers in various business fields. In the words of Uchefuna (2013), Business Education programme is a systematic and organized process of instruction designed to equip students with the knowledge, skills and attitudes vital for effective performance in business and economic activities. Business Education therefore prepares students to start, manage or work in businesses. Okeke-Ezeanyawu and Okpala (2021), opined that the Business Education programme is an educational tertiary institution that equips the recipients with the knowledge and skills for establishing and managing a business venture. It is vital to note that, for Business Education programme particularly in universities to function, there is need for strategies.

Strategies are long-term plans of action designed to achieve specific goals or objectives. In Business Education, strategies refers to deliberate plans and approaches to achieve specific learning objectives, enhance students engagement, and develop essential skills for future business professionals.

Business Education, strategies involve the integration of teaching methods, learning techniques and assessments procedures to promote effective learning outcomes in Business Education (Nwosu, 2018). However, strategies here is refer to Business, Education through Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Improving Business Education programme through Artificial Intelligence (AI), involves leveraging AI technologies to enhance teaching, learning and assessment. According to Nick (2014), AI refers to the development of computer systems that can perform tasks that typically require human intelligence such as learning, Reasoning, Problem-solving, perception and decision-making. AI can also be defined as intelligence machine that thinks and learn like humans.

In this context, personalized-related strategies and intelligent tutoring-related strategies will be discussed. With these strategies, Business Education programme will be improved through AI.

Personalized learning-related strategies are instructional approaches tailored to individual students, needs, interests, and learning styles. These strategies aim to increase student's engagement, motivation and academic success. This is in agreement with Uchefuna (2022) that personalized learning-related strategies caters to diverse learners needs including those with disabilities. Moreover, Ogunji (2015) opined that, a personalized approach adjusts instruction to match individual learners pace, style and abilities. By integrating AI, Business Education programme can enhance student's engagement and improve learning outcomes. Apart from personalized learning-related strategies, intelligent tutoring strategies will improve Business Education programme..

Intelligent tutoring system (ITS) are computer-based educational systems that provide personalized instruction and feedback to students. According to Uchefuna (2022), these strategies are cognitive tutoring, intelligent mentoring, collaborative learning and simulation-based learning. Intelligent tutoring no doubt, improve students engagement and increased efficiency.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has demonstrated capacity in promoting knowledge acquisition across all level and programmes of 21st century education system. The use of AI has benefited various programmes. But is Business Education programme in Universities in Enugu state affected? In attempt to answer this .work on strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state was carried out.

Statement of the problem

Artificial Intelligence is a computer system capable of performing complex tasks that historically only a human could do, such as reasoning, making decisions or solving problems. Business Education programme in other word is a structured educational initiative that teaches student, the competencies needed to succeed in Business, preparing them for careers in various business fields.

Despite the critical role of Business Education in equipping her recipients with essential skills for the workforce; records have it that some factors may be lacking. Business Education programme seem not to reflect the dynamic needs of modern business environment, leading to a mismatch between graduate skills and industry requirements. Again, stakeholders are worried over outdated infrastructure and limited access to technology, AI inclusive.

It is against this backdrop that, strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state was carried out.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to determine strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine personalized related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.
2. Ascertain the intelligent tutoring-related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the personalized related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state?

2. What are the intelligent tutoring-related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state?

Hypotheses

The under listed hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test

Ho1: there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively on personalized related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

Ho2: there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal Universities and their counterparts in State on the intelligent tutoring related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

Method

A descriptive survey research design was employed in this study. According to Nworgu (2015), descriptive survey is the one in which a group of people is studied by collecting and analyzing data from few people considered to be representative of the entire group. The study was carried out in two government owned Universities in Enugu state (University of Nigeria, Nsukka and Enugu state University of Science and Technology). The population for the study comprised of 24 Business Educators from University of Nigeria, Nsukka and 6 from Enugu state University of Science and Technology respectively totaling 30 Business Educators. There was no sampling, because the population size was manageable.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers entitled: Strategies for Improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire (SFIBEPITAIQ). The instrument has three sections. Section A was on bio-data. Section B on the Personalized related strategies and section C contains items on Intelligent tutoring-related strategies. The rating responses were strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with numerical value of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts. Two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education (Measurements and Evaluation) both from Enugu state University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu State. To test the reliability of the instrument, 20 Business Educators in government owned Universities in Anambra State was used. Cronbach Alpha estimate was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument; which yielded a coefficient index of 0.69. this index indicated that, the instrument was reliable enough to be used for the study.

The researchers with the help of three research assistants used direct delivery techniques in the administration of the instrument to the respondents. At the end of the administration of the instrument, all the 30 copies were returned and used for the study; representing 100% rate of return. Mean and standard deviation was used in answering the research questions; while t-test was used in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at the appropriate degree of freedom

Decision rule for answering the research questions was based on the real limits of the mean this:

Strongly Agree - 3.50 - 4.00

Agree - 2.50 - 3.49

Disagree - 1.50 - 2.49

Strongly Disagree - 1.00 - 1.49

For the hypotheses, when the calculated t-value was equal to or greater than the table value, the null hypotheses was rejected, otherwise it was rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the personalized related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation of Business Educators in the personalized related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

S/N	Items	Federal N=24		State N=6		Overall N=30		Decision
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	X	SD	
1	AI creates customized learning pathways tailored to individual student's needs.	3.25	0.84	3.05	0.86	3.15		Agree
2	AI provides more accurate measure of skills	3.16	1.02	3.02	0.79	3.09		Agree
3	It provides immediate targeted feedback to stakeholders	3.12	0.86	2.92	0.82	3.02		Agree
4	AI focuses instruction on specific skills student need to develop	2.81	0.89	2.86	1.03	2.84		Agree
5	It help students explore potential career paths	2.96	0.99	2.94	1.04	2.95		Agree
6	AI analyzes individual student data to identify trends, inform instruction.	3.00	1.10	3.07	0.92	3.04		Agree
7	AI assigns projects tailored to individual students learning objectives.	2.84	0.88	2.22	0.96	2.53		Agree
8	AI powered platforms connect students with peers, mentors, industry professionals for collaborative learning	2.36	0.88	2.26	0.99	2.31		Agree
9	AI driven coaching system provides personalized guidance to students	3.23	0.82	3.24	0.84	3.34		Agee
10	AI creates detailed profiles of students SWOT to inform instruction	3.13	1.03	3.04	1.02	3.09		Agree
	Cluster mean/SD	2.09	0.93	2.86	0.93	2.93		Agree

Table 1, shows that items of 3.15, 3.09, 3.02, 2.84, 2.95, 3.04, 2.53, 2.31, 3.24 and 3.09 respectively are regarded as agreed by the respondents. The grand mean value of 2.93 also attested to that; while cluster standard deviation of 0.93 shows homogeneity of opinions of the respondents.

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal Universities and their counterparts in State on the personalized related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

Table 2: Summary table of t-test analysis of mean scores of Business Educators in Federal Universities and their counterparts in State type on the personalized related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

Status	No	\bar{x}	SD	DF	t-table	t-cal	Decision
Federal	24	2.99	0.93	28	1.96	0.48	NS
State	06	2.86	0.93				

Table 2 shows that, the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 28 degree of freedom is 0.48; while the table value or critical value under the same conditions is 1.96. Since the calculated t-value is less than the critical or table value, the null hypotheses is therefore not significant.

This is invariably mean that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal Universities and their counterparts in the state type on personalized related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

Research Question 2: what are intelligent tutoring-related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state?

Table 3: Mean scores and standard deviation of Business Educators on Intelligent tutoring-related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

S/N	Items	Federal N=24		State N=6		Overall N=30		Decision
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	X	SD	
11	AI-powered tutoring systems provide individualized support to students mimicking human tutors.	2.81	0.96	2.24	0.98	2.53		Agree
12	AI-powered chatbots for student support	2.90	0.99	2.60	0.92	2.75		Agree
13	It enhance text analysis for business case studies	1.76	0.94	2.39	0.97	2.08		Agree
14	AI-powered plagiarism detection	1.46	0.75	1.45	0.88	1.46		Agree
15	It powered alumni networking	2.06	1.01	2.01	1.04	2.04		Agree
16	Enhance learning analytics for curriculum improvement	1.44	0.80	1.27	0.61	1.36		Agree
17	AI-powered educational data mining	1.47	0.84	1.23	0.63	1.35		Agree
18	Enhance recommender systems for career development	1.38	0.61	1.25	0.68	1.32		Agree
19	Predictive analytics for student performance							Agree

		1.40	0.83	1.27	0.59	1.34	
20	Intelligent learning pace adjustment	1.46	0.88	1.37	0.82	1.42	Agree
	Cluster mean/SD	1.81	0.88	1.71	0.82	1.76	Agree

Results data in Table 3 above, reveals that items 11 to 20 with scores of 2.53, 2.75, 2.08, 1.46, 2.04, 1.36, 1.35, 1.32, 1.34 and 1.42 respectively are regarded as agreed by the respondents. The grand mean value of 1.76 also attested to that; while cluster standard deviation of 0.82 shows homogeneity of opinions of the respondents.

Hypotheses 2

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State universities respectively on intelligent tutoring related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

Table 4: Summary Table of t-test analysis of mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State universities respectively on intelligent tutoring-related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

Status	No	\bar{x}	SD	DF	t-table	t-cal	Decision
Federal	24	1.81	0.88	28	1.96	0.38	NS
State	06	1.71	0.82				

Table 4 shows that, the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 28 degree of freedom is 0.38; while the table value or critical value under the same conditions is 1.96. Since the calculated t-value is less than the critical value, the null hypotheses is therefore not significant.

This means that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State universities respectively on intelligent tutoring-related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state.

Discussion of Findings

The data presented in Table 1, showed that Business Educators in Federal and State universities in Enugu state were in agreement that personalized-related strategies improves Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence. These strategies are creation of customized learning pathways tailored to individual students, helping students explore potential career paths among others.

The findings are in line with Uchefuna (2022) that personalized learning strategies caters to diverse learners needs including those with disabilities.

The null hypotheses one tested on the Personalized showed that, there was no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State universities on personalized related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that the status of University had no significant influence in their opinions.

Data obtained regarding research question two, revealed that Business Educators in Federal and State universities in Enugu state were in agreement that, intelligent tutoring-related strategies are needed for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence.

The null hypotheses two tested, showed that Business Educators in Federal Universities and their counterparts in State type did not differ significantly in their mean scores on intelligent tutoring-related strategies for improving Business Education programme in Universities through Artificial Intelligence in Enugu state. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that the status of universities had no significant influence in their opinions.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study that it was concluded that Business Education programme in Universities in Enugu state improved through Artificial Intelligence contrary to the reports trending owing some organization that Business Education graduates perform poorly in classrooms and offices.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended that;

1. Personalized teaching technique should be a course of its own.
2. Business Educators should be exposed to artificial intelligence tools and skills.

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